

Arthaśāstra

By Aaron Michael Ullrey, University of Houston, University of Naropa

Entry tags: Religious Group, Text, Sanskrit literature, Nītiśāstra, Hinduism

A wide-spanning treatise (sastra) on prosperity or rule (artha). This text has been labelled non-religious because it is not revealed scripture (sauté) and because it treats "realpolitik", economics, statecraft, and war. That said, the text also describes early practices of yogis and magicians (yogamantravid) who, intriguingly, were often employed as spies. Throughout the Arthasastra the real world actions were connected also with herbology and magic and portents; in this way there is not a clear distinction between religious and nonreligious. The text is supposedly based on a Mauryan emperor, and its start and recensions are found from 200 BCE-200 CE. This text shows the political world and background that would have informed composition of the epic Mahabharata and Ramayana. This text sets out a system of government in which various kingdoms interact, leading to a notion that the enemy of my enemy is my friend, so a ruler must activate relationships with the next neighbor kingdom against the immediate kingdoms. Overall this is a book about the running of a kingdom and maintaining relationships with rival kingdoms, the audience should be considered kings and their counselors. This text describes the work of mines and trade, extensively explaining a sort of "ideal" political world. That said, the text is more often compared to Machiavelli's The Prince rather than Palto's The Republic. A ruler is to be devisions and employs spies (often yogis), to consult royal magicians and military advisors (purohita), to interpret portents, and to engage magical as well as physical warfare. Traditionally there are four aims of life, purusharth: sex (kama), business (artha), dharma (religious practice), and moksha (liberation). Artha here should be considered rule, money, trade, prestige, and economics. "Dharma is the root of happiness. Artha is the root of Dharma. Kingship/Power is the root of Artha. And kingship/power is rooted in self-governance (indriya), and truly regulated behavior is rooted in self-governance. Well-regulated behavior is based on serving the the elderly elders (vriddha). There is an extensive discussion of bureaucracy in the kingdom that predates usual south asian beaurocratic ideas rooted in Persian culture. Kangle divides his treatments of the Arthasastra into explorations of the state, society and social life, state economy, state administration, law and justice, internal security, defense, relationships with rival kingdoms. The fifteen books are divided so the first five regard tantra, here meaning internal administration of the state (ganatantra is the modern word for the Indian republic), the next eight deal with āvāpa, here meaning neighboring states, and the last two are miscellaneous, consisting of "secret practices" that include a wide range of nasty processes from magic to biowarfare to counter magic against malicious spell craft. Further esoteric practices are general spellcraft not just for warfare but for courtly life including erotic materials magical domination, invisible spells. The final chapter is a brief description of "sciences" that are sort of vague principles to be applied to earlier topics, some of these principles are cross referenced to earlier descriptions in the text.

Date Range: 300 BCE - 200 CE

Region: General Northern South Asia, Gujarat to Bengal

Region tags: Hinduism

Generally Northern with mention of regions far west and far east of South Asia.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Olivelle Patrick and Mark McClish. 2012. *The Arthashastra Selections from the Classic Indian Work on Statecraft*. Indianapolis: Hackett Publishing Company.
<http://public.eblib.com/choice/publicfullrecord.aspx?p=1014672>.
- Source 2: Kauṭalya Kauṭalya and R. P Kangle. 1969. *The Kauṭīliya Arthaśāstra*. 2nd ed. Bombay: University of Bombay.
- Source 3: McClish Mark. 2020. *The History of the Arthashastra : Sovereignty and Sacred Law in Ancient India*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Notes: Olivelle is the most prominent contemporary scholar on the Arthashastra. Kangle's translation is the classic.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.indiatoday.in/education-today/gk-and-current-affairs/story/kautilyas-arthashastra-quick-overview-248624-2015-04-15>
- Source 1 Description: Quick Overview from Indian Press
- Source 2 URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Arthashastra>
- Source 2 Description: Wikipedia
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-021-00888-6>
- Source 3 Description: Article by Dar that shows the importance of this text.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://ncjindalps.com/pdf/HUMANITIES/The%20Kautilya%20Arthashastra%20-%20Chanakya.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: Translation of Arthashastra
- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/kangle1960>
- Source 2 Description: Kangle study, translation, and transcription
- Source 3 URL: <https://ia801400.us.archive.org/9/items/KautilyaKaArthshastra-Hindi-Kautilya/10.Kautilya-arthshastra.pdf>
- Source 3 Description: Hindi study and translation

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

–with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

–Specify: Varied mediums. Manuscripts would have been on palm leaf but there are paper mss attestations later. Printed as a modern book now.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: Due to its time period, there are no temples nor are found the classic "trinity" of Hindu deities.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: Varied versions. Likely three distinct recensions.

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Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: The text was written supposedly by an emperor, Kautilya, but it was most likely compiled from many sources written by brahmin couriers and then unified and given an author attestation.

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the modern audience is historians, politicians, and so forth, the original audience would have been land owning governors (ksatriyas), or, rather the brahmins they employed to advise on statecraft and warfare.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: Would not be considered revealed or particularly reverential.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The Sanskrit prose, and occasional verses, are not like liturgical sanskrit.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: Rituals are prescribed but not with extensive directions, and the text would not be recited.

Is there material significance to the text?

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: This text should be considered to have the philosophical and metaphysical context of early "Hinduism" with the related ascetic challenges of Buddhism and Jainism.

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural creatures and deities are present, but in the text there is little about them and nothing about their agency.

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

Notes: General notions of happy goods and beings meaning a happy, prosperous kingdom. But it is vague.

- ↳ Libations?
 - Yes
- ↳ Food?
 - Yes
- ↳ Animal sacrifice?
 - No
- ↳ Human sacrifice?
 - No
- ↳ Sacred objects?
 - No
- ↳ Daily life objects?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: A collection of sections/chapters on a wide range of rituals and policies and statecraft.

Notes: The chapters toward the end on magic rituals and sciences have a wide range of ritual details, though are not complete ritual prescriptions.

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Ascetics would be celibate. But celibacy is not an ideal for normal people or rulers. This is an era of quite wide-ranging eroticism, especially for the elite. Similar world and worldview as Kamasutra.

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: This whole text is about how to rule and manage customs and manage subjects.

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: The text makes reference to a number of other authors like Bharadvaja, another famous author of the time. Of course, Kautilya is always the final authority in the text. So other points of contention are brought up so Kautiliya can argue against them or nuance them.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: No mention of afterlife.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

Notes: Men are mostly free to pursue others. However, we see them being fined for taking a woman who was secured for another, courtesan relationships, sex during menstruation.

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

Notes: Many punishments are laid out for women regarding virginity (including fines for deflowering herself or deflowering by another woman). Adultery is defined by the level of "enjoyments" ranging from touching hair to actual sex.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: Men should have appropriate partners. However we read quite a bit about punishments for approaching/having sex with an inappropriate partner. Prostitutes may not be taken by force. Sexual action outside of the female organ or misbehaving with a man are minor punishments and fines. That said "A fine of twelve pandas is prescribed for the senseless wretch who carnally approaches lower animals, and double (that) for misbehaving with images of the gods" (AŚ 4.13.41) Kangle 291)

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Notes: Female sexual behavior regulated by patriarchy. There are elements of adultery punishments being variable. Appropriate marriage partners are regulated.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

Notes: The text sets out legal and moral systems. There are some people outside of that system, like ascetics, but every "normal" subject would be under the conventions of this text. The morality does resonate with other legal texts like the Manusmṛiti.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– No

Notes: Not clear here, but it would be in the background.

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– No

Notes: Not explicit but present.

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– Yes

Notes: Karma and dharma. Also the balance of cosmic order, ritu.

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– No

Notes: Deities at the time were not very anthropomorphic, but the person, the man, the anthropo was different at the time. The only properly human looking deity at the time would have been Indra.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– No

Notes: Moral norms are almost always related to smṛti, remembered texts, texts authored by humans. The authors may be considered sages, but often their authority is not based on personal status, rather the more authoritative law codes and moralities are those that are the most complete and extensive.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– I don't know

Notes: The moral norms are thought to be sorta self-evident and mechanical. That said, violations can cause calamities, and all calamities have some connection to non-human beings.

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: Especially rulers and beuarcrats. But there are legal punishments for adulterers, aborters, traitors, murderers, and attackers.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: Three recensions of manuscript. Varied translations today into English and into Hindi.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: Castration as a punishment for certain sexual transgressions.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: Proper rule via the text will lead to prosperity for the king and kingdom.

Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

Notes: Notions of rule and discipline are found, there were groups of police like members in institutions. Specific chapters are given for the regulation of the public and dispensing of punishments.

Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The legal code of the Manusmriti is the foundation of much Hindu law, and the Artha sastra is in this same genre. Productive comparisons can be made between the Arthasastra and the Manusmriti to reveal a prescriptive view of past society in South Asia.

Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

Execution?

– Yes

Notes: Varies punishments of execution for traitors or women who have murdered. There are a number of gruesome execution descriptions/prescriptions

in chapter 4.11. Of note aborotioinists are killed, murderes, and assaulters, as well as traitors to the king.

↳ Exile?

– I don't know

Notes: Problematic men are sent off, out of the kingdom. Regulations of punishment are highest (death), middling (corporal punishment or exile), or lowest (money fines).

↳ Corporal punishments?

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the perceived severity a person might have limbs removed or be disfigured. At the extreme are corporal punishment leading to death, including death with/by torture.

↳ Ostracism?

– I don't know

Notes: Some general discussion of ostracizing for such transgressions as ostracism,

↳ Seizure of property?

– Yes

Notes: Seizure of property from all enemies and traitors.

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Those who fit into the structure well will be rewarded through prosperity.....included here are ap[pointments to positions for generating wealth like mining or dam regulating.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: No described, but there would have been an underlying element of reincarnation.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: It is considered a treatise on leadership, *nītiśāstra*. And it is associated with the first great empire of India, the Mauryans.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: The text is mostly set after its third recensions.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

Notes: While this is considered a non-religious text, it has a fair amount of religious contents. It is considered one of the earliest and most important ant of these treatises on ruling and politics.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Notes: That said it is a part of the wider genre of *Nitisastra*.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: This text almost resists virtues in favor of *realpolitik*. That said, following virtues including sexual propriety with spouse and appropriate partners, submission to the system of morality, and loyal patronage to a king who himself acts freely out of his own will....these are aspects of a moral order and sets of ideals.

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: Only to fulfill local festival vows. Presumably there would be temporary vows on fasting days.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Notes: There is a sense that cremation grounds and other funeral sites ought to be at the edge of the kingdom.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: This is part of the larger genre and canon on treatises of rule/politics, nītiśāstra

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: Some notions of months and calendar but no clear official calendar. Arguments throughout that local holidays and deities ought to be maintained, even if they conflict with the practices of the rulers.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: There is a surprising lack of regulation of food purity, which also suggest that this is a text not intended for brahmins. Also, vegetarianism is not advanced anywhere.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Notes: Corporal punishment for treachery and sexual impropriety,

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: Indication the funeral areas are impure and at the edge of a city.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Local and trans local deities referred to but not specifically. No specific worship rituals. It is a world though that has spirit beings and deities.

A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: Polytheistic religion. However, each king would patronize a specific deity and that deity would organize any "official religion" of the kingdom, though that king might also support Buddhists and Jains.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: Generally Hinduism will posit apotheosis of great kings, saints, and holy people. But there are no specific details here.

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Notes: This is a time before temples and images of deities.

Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: The beings manipulated in magic can cause a direct effect, feeling.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Sukra and Brihaspati are invoked at several points, there are the purohitas (main priests) for the Gods (deva) and the antigods (asura)

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: The divine purohitas were experts in statecraft.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: This would apply to regional deities, but not to deities in general.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Higher sectarian deities would have unrestricted knowledge, but the deities in this text are vague.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– I don't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– I don't know

Notes: Deities are different here than in later Hinduism where deities do know the innermost heart.

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– I don't know

Notes: The notions of divinity here do not seem to have a great concern for individuals.

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Notes: Yogis and magicians are thought to be in communication with non-human forces, and the king is advised to consult them.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings and portents can affect the kingdom or outcomes in war. But the emphasis is on the this-worldly regulation of the kingdom.

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Notes: Around this same time, there is a worship of warfare goddesses associated with victory such as Shreya. Also, we first see Durga arising toward the end of this period. Durga, difficult to approach, is also a word for a castle or military fortification.

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Notes: Specific punishing beings are not listed, but supernatural beings, as we can see from texts like the Atharvaveda (written right before this) that the world is filled with unpleasant beings that can afflict to punish but also afflict out of their own capriciousness.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Notes: The purohit, head priest, would interpret spirits and portents, but there is not clear communication with normal folk.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: The general background of the text, while not directly stated, is that there are supernatural beings affecting everything.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: All Indic religions have a background of hungry spirits.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: There are no temples at this time, which only start in the 6th century. They kings and the wealthy would have presumably sponsored vedic rituals which would require the donation of many goods.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: Surprisingly few details. Assume the deities would be the major vedic ones like Indra, Soma, Agni, and so forth. That said, it is unclear whether the texts would or would not accept buddhist or Jain pantheons. Also, no mention of Surya (the sun) who would have had an active cult at the time. Inscriptions from this time show kings supporting varied institutions depending on the location and who their subject were. Mauryas were known for being Buddhists and Jains but they would still support brahmin camps and Vedic rituals.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: There are clerical experts but not really saints.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: It does describe the comportment and behavior of soldiers and spies.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: The supernatural beings are vague but they are not invoked by the text.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: Ethics appropriate for each individual. Legal regulations are set out widely regarding violence, sexual propriety, and economics/bureaucracy.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Paranormal?

Notes: There will be a wide variety of deities, but the text avoids describing them in favor of Realpolitik and administration.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– I don't know

Notes: There are margins in places for ascetics and yogis. But the real outgroup would be the immediate neighbor kingdoms, who must be manipulated to insure a kingdom's prosperity.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: But the king is advised to have his purohit consult magicians and yogis to discern risks or portents. Presumably they may have used divination and informed the purohit and then the king.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Varied rituals, but few described. Brahmins at the time had extensive rituals, and those sponsoring brahmin would have supported their rituals and performed certain rituals themselves. Jains and Buddhist had varied daily rituals that were different.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

Notes: Depends on the rituals, the kinds would do many vedic sovereignty rites

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– I don't know

Notes: This also really depends on the rituals. This is a time of extensive rituals, so some would be long and with great weight, and others would have been brief, especially domestic ones. It appears that war magic was done regularly during times of conflict and combat.

Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: Brahmin authorities.

Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: Brahmin authorities.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Notes: Generally at the time the only intoxicant used in rituals would be Soma, whatever that is. Certain types of alcohol seem possible, and there is a regulation that there are four vices springing from lust: hunting, gambling, women, and drink. One thinker says that drink has enjoyments, but Kautilya describes the dangers of drink: losing consciousness, acting crazy, appearing like a corpse, exposing genitals, loss of learning and strength and wealth and friends, associating with the harmful, and becoming obsessed with song.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: Assuming brahmins are performing vedic rituals, then the roles of each participant will be constrained by caste and jati markers.

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: No.....but it describes entertaining practices such as festivals.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: Kings are described setting out taxation revenues from certain villages that would be used to support brahmin camps.

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: Three recensions of manuscript. Varied translations today into English and into Hindi.

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– Yes

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: A collection of sections/chapters on a wide range of rituals and policies and statecraft.

Notes: The chapters toward the end on magic rituals and sciences have a wide range of ritual details,

though are not complete ritual prescriptions.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: The text makes reference to a number of other authors like Bharadvaja, another famous author of the time. Of course, Kautilya is always the final authority in the text. So other points of contention are brought up so Kautilya can argue against them or nuance them.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: Proper rule via the text will lead to prosperity for the king and kingdom.

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

Notes: Notions of rule and discipline are found, there were groups of police like members in institutions. Specific chapters are given for the regulation of the public and dispensing of punishments.

↳ Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The legal code of the Manusmriti is the foundation of much Hindu law, and the Artha sastra is in this same genre. Productive comparisons can be made between the Arthasastra and the Manusmriti to reveal a prescriptive view of past society in South Asia.

↳ Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

↳ Execution?

– Yes

Notes: Varies punishments of execution for traitors or women who have murdered. There are a number of gruesome execution descriptions/prescriptions in chapter 4.11. Of note abortionists are killed, murderers, and assaulters, as well as traitors to the king.

↳ Exile?

– I don't know

Notes: Problematic men are sent off, out of the kingdom. Regulations of punishment are highest (death), middling (corporal punishment or exile), or lowest (money fines).

↳ Corporal punishments?

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the perceived severity a person might have limbs removed or be disfigured. At the extreme are corporal punishment leading to death, including death with/by torture.

↳ Ostracism?

– I don't know

Notes: Some general discussion of ostracizing for such transgressions as ostracism,

↳ Seizure of property?

– Yes

Notes: Seizure of property from all enemies and traitors.

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Those who fit into the structure well will be rewarded through prosperity.....included here are ap[pointments to positions for generating wealth like mining or dam regulating.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: Some notions of months and calendar but no clear official calendar. Arguments throughout that local holidays and deities ought to be maintained, even if they conflict with the practices of the rulers.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: This text should be considered to have the philosophical and metaphysical context of early "Hinduism" with the related ascetic challenges of Buddhism and Jainism.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: No mention of afterlife.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: No described, but there would have been an underlying element of reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: There is a sense that cremation grounds and other funeral sites ought to be at the edge of the kingdom.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: Indication the funeral areas are impure and at the edge of a city.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Local and trans local deities referred to but not specifically. No specific worship rituals. It is a world though that has spirit beings and deities.

A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: Polytheistic religion. However, each king would patronize a specific deity and that deity would organize any "official religion" of the kingdom, though that king might also support Buddhists and Jains.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: Generally Hinduism will posit apotheosis of great kings, saints, and holy people. But there are no specific details here.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Notes: This is a time before temples and images of deities.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: The beings manipulated in magic can cause a direct effect, feeling.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Sukra and Brihaspati are invoked at several points, there are the purohitas (main priests) for the Gods (deva) and the antigods (asura)

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: The divine purohitas were experts in statecraft.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: This would apply to regional deities, but not to deities in general.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Higher sectarian deities would have unrestricted knowledge, but the deities in this text are vague.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– I don't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– I don't know

Notes: Deities are different here than in later Hinduism where deities do know the innermost heart.

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– I don't know

Notes: The notions of divinity here do not seem to have a great concern for individuals.

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Notes: Yogis and magicians are thought to be in communication with non-human forces, and the king is advised to consult them.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings and portents can affect the kingdom or outcomes in war. But the emphasis is on the this-worldly regulation of the kingdom.

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Notes: Around this same time, there is a worship of warfare goddesses associated with victory such as Shreya. Also, we first see Durga arising toward the end of this period. Durga, difficult to approach, is also a word for a castle or military fortification.

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Notes: Specific punishing beings are not listed, but supernatural beings, as we can see from texts like the Atharvaveda (written right before this) that the world is filled with unpleasant beings that can afflict to punish but also afflict out of their own capriciousness.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Notes: The purohit, head priest, would interpret spirits and portents, but there is not clear communication with normal folk.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: The general background of the text, while not directly stated, is that there are supernatural beings affecting everything.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: All Indic religions have a background of hungry spirits.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: Surprisingly few details. Assume the deities would be the major vedic ones like Indra, Soma, Agni, and so forth. That said, it is unclear whether the texts would or would not accept buddhist or Jain pantheons. Also, no mention of Surya (the sun) who would have had an active cult at the time. Inscriptions from this time show kings supporting varied institutions depending on the location and who their subject were. Mauryas were known for being Buddhists and Jains but they would still support brahmin camps and Vedic rituals.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: There are clerical experts but not really saints.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: The supernatural beings are vague but they are not invoked by the text.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Paranormal?

Notes: There will be a wide variety of deities, but the text avoids describing them in favor of Realpolitik

and administration.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: But the king is advised to have his purohit consult magicians and yogis to discern risks or portents. Presumably they may have used divination and informed the purohit and then the king.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural creatures and deities are present, but in the text there is little about them and nothing about their agency.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

Notes: General notions of happy goods and beings meaning a happy, prosperous kingdom. But it is vague.

↳ Libations?

– Yes

↳ Food?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– No

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Sacred objects?

– No

↳ Daily life objects?

– No

- ↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: This whole text is about how to rule and manage customs and manage subjects.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

Notes: The text sets out legal and moral systems. There are some people outside of that system, like ascetics, but every "normal" subject would be under the conventions of this text. The morality does resonate with other legal texts like the Manusmṛiti.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– No

Notes: Not clear here, but it would be in the background.

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– No

Notes: Not explicit but present.

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– Yes

Notes: Karma and dharma. Also the balance of cosmic order, ritu.

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– No

Notes: Deities at the time were not very anthropomorphic, but the person, the man, the anthropo was different at the time. The only properly human looking deity at the time would have been Indra.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– No

Notes: Moral norms are almost always related to smṛti, remembered texts, texts authored by humans. The authors may be considered sages, but often their authority is not based on personal status, rather the more authoritative law codes and moralities are those that are the most complete and extensive.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– I don't know

Notes: The moral norms are thought to be sorta self-evident and mechanical. That said, violations can cause calamities, and all calamities have some connection to non-human beings.

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: Especially rulers and beuarocrats. But there are legal punishments for adulterers, aborters, traitors, murderers, and attackers.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: This text almost resists virtues in favor of realpolitik. That said, following virtues including sexual prprietty with spouse and appropriate partners, submission to the system of morality, and loyal patronage to a king who himself acts freely out of his own will....these are aspects of a moral order and sets of ideals.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Ascetics would be celibate. But celibacy is not an ideal for normal people or rulers. This is an era of quite wide-ranging eroticism, especially for the elite. Similar world and worldview as Kamasutra.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

Notes: Men are mostly free to peursue others. However, we see them being fined for taking a woman who was secured for another, courtesan relationships, sex during menstruation.

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

Notes: Many punishments are laid out for women regarding virginity (including fines for deflowering herself or deflowering by another women). Adultery is defined by the level of "enjoyments" ranging from touching hair to actual sex.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: Men should have appropriate partners. However we read quite a bit about punishments for approaching/having sex with an inappropriate partner. Prostitutes may not be taken by force. Sexual action outside of the female organ or misbehaving with a man are minor punishments and fines. That said "A fine of twelve pandas is prescribed for the senseless wretch who carnally approaches lower animals, and double (that) for misbehaving with images of the gods" (AŚ 4.13.41) Kangle 291)

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Notes: Female sexual behavior regulated by patriarchy. There are elements of adultery punishments being variable. Appropriate marriage partners are regulated.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: Castration as a punishment for certain sexual transgressions.

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: Only to fulfill local festival vows. Presumably there would be temporary vows on fasting days.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: There is a surprising lack of regulation of food purity, which also suggest that this is a text not intended for brahmins. Also, vegetarianism is not advanced anywhere.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Notes: Corporal punishment for treachery and sexual impropriety,

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: There are no temples at this time, which only start in the 6th century. They kings and the wealthy would have presumably sponsored vedic rituals which would require the donation of many goods.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: It does describe the comportment and behavior of soldiers and spies.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: Ethics appropriate for each individual. Legal regulations are set out widely regarding violence, sexual propriety, and economics/bureaucracy.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– I don't know

Notes: There are margins in places for ascetics and yogis. But the real outgroup would be the immediate neighbor kingdoms, who must be manipulated to insure a kingdoms prosperity.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Varied rituals, but few described. Brahmins at the time had extensive rituals, and those sponsoring brahmin would have supported their rituals and performed certain rituals themselves. Jains and Buddhist had varied daily rituals that were different.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

Notes: Depends on the rituals, the kinds would do many vedic sovereignty rites

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– I don't know

Notes: This also really depends on the rituals. This is a time of extensive rituals, so some would be long and with great weight, and others would have been brief, especially domestic ones. It appears that war magic was done regularly during times of conflict and combat.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: Brahmin authorities.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: Brahmin authorities.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Notes: Generally at the time the only intoxicant used in rituals would be Soma, whatever that is. Certain types of alcohol seem possible, and there is a regulation that there are four vices springing from lust: hunting, gambling, women, and drink. One thinker says that drink has enjoyments, but Kautilya describes the dangers of drink: losing consciousness, acting crazy, appearing like a corpse, exposing genitals, loss of learning and strength and wealth and friends, associating with the harmful, and becoming obsessed with song.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: Assuming brahmins are performing vedic rituals, then the roles of each participant will be constrained by caste and jati markers.

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: No.....but it describes entertaining practices such as festivals.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: Kings are described setting out taxation revenues from certain villages that would be used to support brahmin camps.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

Notes: Tons of information here. There various positions in the court relate to the kings. And all the different positions in the kingdom are related to one another in a formal way,

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

Notes: Distinct economic descriptions, trade, mining and how property is related to the king.

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

Notes: Kings and royalty would support brahmin encampments (garabara)

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– Yes

Notes: Extensive description of rent and lease and economics of property.

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– I don't know

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

Notes: Extensive discussion of warfare organization and practices of war. This also includes magical support of war and spying. Also there are even elements of biowarfare.

↳ Power to conscript?

– I don't know

Notes: It would seem that soldiers would be from the kingly-landowning-military caste. I do not see evidence of forceful conscription.

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– I don't know

Notes: This is hard to argue. The armies would only operate during warfare season, the post monsoon fall and winter.

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– Yes

Notes: There are various descriptions of the standing armies, the movements of armies, and the regulation of armies in forts. The comportment of soldiers and commanders of soldiers are quite detailed.

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– Yes

Notes: Varied discussions of military training.

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Yes

Notes: An emperor should affiliate with the enemies of his neighbor in order to sure up peace or to find success in war.

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Notes: There are many many descriptions of battle and disruption of rule, and many ways to

avoid being subjugated. This implies the bemoaning of outer controls.

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: We see a world that has various kingdoms, and an overall empire. There kingdoms and empires are described like a mandala, a set of intersecting circles, but the kingdoms' loyalties alternate. My kingdom surrounded by enemy kingdoms and the enemy kingdoms are surrounded by their enemy kingdoms. The enemy of my enemy should be my ally!

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The religious groups would receive taxes and income from villages decreed by the king to support them.

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– No

Notes: There is a remarkable lack of description of charity. I wonder if charity would be more specifically connected to supporting specific religious groups, and this text is very general about the types of religious groups but there would have been Jains and Buddhists as well as Brahmin vedic ritualists.

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– Yes

Notes: All sorts of regulations on trade and agriculture. There is also the argument that there should be alehouses with many rooms, these are considered sites, as well, for spies.

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– Yes

Notes: Extensive regulations. Agriculture regulations are primarily about specific tracts of lands for specific crops. There are regulations for clearing land. Different crops are prescribed for

specific times and seasons of the year.

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

Notes: So much! A lot happens in the palaces and forts which are described in many details, that said there are offices of agriculture, taxation, courtesan manners, mining, trade, and more.. These would sometimes be in the fort or palace, but these officials would circulate widely.

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

Notes: There are both legal courts and points where the king will regulate from the palaces.

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– Yes

Notes: This text is from east India, most likely, so with wet rice cultivation there are extensive discussions of water issues in the activities of the controllers of shipping, agriculture, pastries, and so forth.

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

Notes: Discussion of transportation is provided for chariots, foot soldiers, and armies, but I do not see other positions for transportation. Some discussion of transportation of valuables from mines to the king's treasury.

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

–Specify: Controllers of mines, wights and measures, royal goldsmith, customs, yarns and textiles, agriculture, animal slaughter, spiritous liquors, courtesans, shipping, cattle, military, credentials, and city superintendents. Secret agents were use extensively by the king to spy in his kingdom and in foreign kingdoms, these spies were regulated like a public work.

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– Yes

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Brahmin groups supported by the taxation and wealth from villages granted to them by the kings. We rice cultivation. Varied forms of crops for fields supplying the palace and city.

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: At the time there was not extensive vegetarianism, outside of Jainism. The brahmins would have had more regulations on purity and impurity. But there is little description about specific food regulations.

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: I am not sure how to nuance this question, "ritual food production" is tricky. There are regulations for agriculture but they do not appear to be specifically ritual. Hunting was considered a vice for it arises from lust, just like drinking and gambling.

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: This genre of Nitisastra would have been studied extensively by rulers and the brahmin advisors.

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: The text describes poverty but it also describes kings supporting the poor. That said there are few institutions for poverty support. There are a number of trade and agriculture sections that regulate distribution, but charity is not declared.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Segmentary Lineage

Notes: Brahmin custodial, but Ksatriya topic and Vaishya topics. That said, Sanskrit was known by all three upper castes, and the text could circulate. But the text would mostly have been distributed among brahmins who were advising kings. That said, a Buddhist figure could apply these same principles if advising a king.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are organizations that train students in various stages of life to various ends.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: The old are explicitly called to be cared for.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Notes: It is hard to separate the religious and nonreligious, but we can see that this would be a non-ritual education, an education in how to live and rule.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: Brahmins would have been the key teachers and educators.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Education would be entirely male, but there are elements of courtesan culture in which women would have been well educated and lettered.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: A ruler must be dedicated to his brahmin purohit.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: Ruling well according to these text principles will lead to prosperity.

Society & Institutions

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Notes: We see a world that has various kingdoms, and an overall empire. There kingdoms and empires are described like a mandala, a set of intersecting circles, but the kingdoms' loyalties alternate. My kingdom surrounded by enemy kingdoms and the enemy kingdoms are surrounded by their enemy kingdoms. The enemy of my enemy should be my ally!

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Public Works

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↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– Yes

Notes: All sorts of regulations on trade and agriculture. There is also the argument that there should be alehouses with many rooms, these are considered sites, as well, for spies.

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– Yes

Notes: Extensive regulations. Agriculture regulations are primarily about specific tracts of lands for specific crops. There are regulations for clearing land. Different crops are prescribed for specific times and seasons of the year.

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

Notes: So much! A lot happens in the palaces and forts which are described in many details, that said there are offices of agriculture, taxation, courtesan manners, mining, trade, and more.. These would sometimes be in the fort or palace, but these officials would circulate widely.

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

Notes: There are both legal courts and points where the king will regulate from the palaces.

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– Yes

Notes: This text is from east India, most likely, so with wet rice cultivation there are extensive discussions of water issues in the activities of the controllers of shipping, agriculture, pastries, and so forth.

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

Notes: Discussion of transportation is provided for chariots, foot soldiers, and armies, but I do not see other positions for transportation. Some discussion of transportation of valuables from mines to the king's treasury.

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: Controllers of mines, wights and measures, royal goldsmith, customs, yarns and textiles, agriculture, animal slaughter, spiritous liquors, courtesans, shipping, cattle, military, credentials, and city superintendents. Secret agents were use extensively by the king to spy in his kingdom and in foreign kingdoms, these spies were regulated like a public work.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The religious groups would receive taxes and income from villages decreed by the king to support them.

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– No

Notes: There is a remarkable lack of description of charity. I wonder if charity would be more specifically connected to supporting specific religious groups, and this text is very general about the types of religious groups but there would have been Jains and Buddhists as well as Brahmin vedic ritualists.

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

Notes: Extensive discussion of warfare organization and practices of war. This also includes magical support of war and spying. Also there are even elements of biowarfare.

↳ Power to conscript?

– I don't know

Notes: It would seem that soldiers would be from the kingly-landowning-military caste. I do not see evidence of forceful conscription.

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– I don't know

Notes: This is hard to argue. The armies would only operate during warfare season, the post monsoon fall and winter.

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– Yes

Notes: There are various descriptions of the standing armies, the movements of armies, and the regulation of armies in forts. The comportment of soldiers and commanders of soldiers are quite detailed.

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– Yes

Notes: Varied discussions of military training.

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Yes

Notes: An emperor should affiliate with the enemies of his neighbor in order to sure up peace or to find success in war.

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Notes: There are many many descriptions of battle and disruption of rule, and many ways to avoid being subjugated. This implies the bemoaning of outer controls.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– Yes

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Brahmin groups supported by the taxation and wealth from villages granted to them by the kings. We rice cultivation. Varied forms of crops for fields supplying the palace and city.

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: At the time there was not extensive vegetarianism, outside of Jainism. The brahmins would have had more regulations on purity and impurity. But there is little description about specific food regulations.

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: I am not sure how to nuance this question, "ritual food production" is tricky. There are regulations for agriculture but they do not appear to be specifically ritual. Hunting was considered a vice for it arises from lust, just like drinking and gambling.

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